

Lie

Introduction

Lying can be defined as when a person tells something untrue to a person, while trying that person to believe that it is actually the truth. In simple words, lying refers to deceive a person. Lying to someone is debatable as it involves many ethical and moral issues. Many people argue that it not morally correct to lie as it may hurt the person who has been deceived when the truth is revealed (Evans, and Kang, pp. 361-362). On the other hand, some people argue that lying is morally correct and inevitable in many circumstances. This essay will discuss the theme of the concept as provided by Machiavelli that how lying is morally right in many cases and also some daily life examples will be discussed which prove that lying in some cases is the best option.

Thesis Statement

Lying is the best option in many circumstances and indeed the best satisfying truth.

Discussion

It is a matter of fact that lying is not a good practice as far as moral values and ethics are concerned. When children grow up they are usually advised by their parents, teachers and other elder people to always speak the truth. It is common observation that lies are not considered

good in any society. However, there are many situations when lying to someone is merely the best choice and something inevitable. In such circumstances, lying helps to prevent other people from any kind of harm and the person himself as well (Joyce, 2007, pp. 8-9). In fact, lying in some circumstances has its own advantages. These advantages can be in the form of protecting someone from being emotionally hurt, protecting someone's life, encouraging peace, etc.

There are many examples from our daily lives which involve lying for the sake of a greater good. To tell the truth, activities which involve lying have been prevailing in our society since a long time ago. Many of the great philosophers and writers of the past including Machiavelli have emphasized deeply on speaking truth in order to encourage and flourish an environment of trust and faith. However, they have also suggested that lying in some conditions is permissible as it prevents us and others as well from any kind of harm. Lying for the benefit of ourselves and others which cause no harm are also known as white lies. In some situations, white lies are in fact the best option and over rule speaking the truth.

The first and the foremost example of lying for the sake of the greater good is trying to protect the life of a person by lying to the person who intends to harm or kill that person. In this case, it appears to be morally correct and as per the ethics to lie to the person about the whereabouts of the person whom he intends to harm or kill (Carson, pp. 42-47). In this way, one person would be saved from being harmed and also the other person would be saved from committing a crime. This tactics of lying is usually common in battles since many centuries.

Another important situation where lying has been suggested as morally correct is when a doctor lies to a patient about any severe disease. In such situations, lying to the patient can be really beneficial for the patient. For instance, if a person is suffering from a dangerous disease, the doctor might not tell him about the actual severity of the disease because it is a human nature

that if someone realizes that he is suffering from a dangerous disease, he may become hopeless and depressed, which will affect the treatment process quite negatively.

Moreover, in today's world almost all advertisements involve lying. This is because of the growing competition in the market and business (Joyce, 2007, pp. 8-9). This practice of lying has also been suggested as morally correct, as long as it does not harm the end users of the goods which are advertised. Furthermore, sometimes lying becomes inevitable in many relationships in order to avoid any conflict. Examples of such relationships are usually formal relationships, but may also include informal as in the case of a husband and wife.

According to various surveys, it has been observed that many husbands lie to their wives when they are asked by their wives about their own beauty and appearance (Evans, and Kang, pp. 362-365). Apart from the relationships, a person can also lie to a thief who is in hurry and asks the person about the amount of money he has or if a thief breaks into a house and asks the owner about the places in the house where the money has been kept.

Conclusion

All in all, lying cannot be justified as morally correct in all circumstances. Nevertheless, there are many situations when lying appears to be the best option as suggested by the great philosopher and writer Machiavelli. In such situations, lying has its own benefits and helps to prevent other people from any kind of harm and the person himself as well.

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